

ECONOMICS

THE MULTIPLIER EFFECT OF THE ZANGEZUR GLOBAL TRANSPORT CORRIDOR IN ACCELERATING THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF AZERBAIJAN

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Abstract

The article examines the multiplicative effect of the Zangezur global transport corridor in accelerating the sustainable development of Azerbaijan. The strategic aspects of the Zangezur Global Transport Corridor are projected in the future. The regional and international advantages of the Zangezur corridor are explained, taking into account the conditions of sustainable development. The potential for accelerating the integration of the countries of the region with the commissioning of the Zangezur corridor is examined. The strategic role of the opening of the Zangezur corridor in unifying the Turkish geography and accelerating the integration of Turkic-speaking states is given. It is substantiated that after the commissioning of the Zangezur corridor, international cargo turnover will increase and cargo transportation will be convenient. Taking modern global challenges as a basis, proposals are made on the strategic aspects of the Zangezur Global Transport Corridor in the context of sustainable development.

Keywords: Azerbaijan, sustainable development, global challenges, Zangezur Global Transport Corridor, strategic aspects of the Zangezur Corridor, prospects of the Zangezur Corridor.

Introduction

Let us note that in modern times, Azerbaijan is living its glorious and honorable history. Thus, the role and historical services of the Azerbaijani state and Azerbaijan in raising the bowed stature of the Turkic world, raising Turkish pride to a new level of awakening, taking bold steps at the world level in liberating the occupied territories, and forming a very beautiful positive example should already be appreciated all over the world. In writing these historical pages, the historical services of the Great Leader Heydar Aliyev, whose 100th anniversary we will celebrate this year, are unforgettable and of strategic importance [1]. After Heydar Aliyev returned to power in Azerbaijan for the second time, starting from mid-1993, historical work was done. As a result of Heydar Aliyev's foresight and unparalleled genius, the "Contract of the Century" was signed on September 20, 1994, and thanks to the implementation of the oil strategy, economic reforms were initiated and the foundation of army building was laid [2, p. 16]. Under the leadership of President Ilham Aliyev, the worthy successor of the Great Leader, the army building has been further accelerated and serious preparations have been made to liberate our occupied lands from the enemy. On the other hand, in the post-pandemic era, which is a global problem, a reassessment of modern realities and definition of goals are required [3].

We would like to note that for many years, peace negotiations with the participation of international organizations and leading world powers have not yielded any results, and Armenia continues to recognize Karabakh as its territory. Since September 27, 2020, the Armenian armed forces and occupiers have been opening fire from various large-caliber weapons, and the Armenians have no intention of leaving Karabakh and liberating the occupied territories, and in response to all this, our brave national army, under the leadership of

the Supreme Commander-in-Chief, launched a counter-attack. During the 44-day battles, our soldiers and officers showed unparalleled heroism and liberated our lands from under the dirty feet of the Armenians, and soon large-scale construction work began in the territories liberated from occupation [4].

Regional and international strategic importance of the Zangezur Global Transport Corridor in the context of sustainable development. Socio-economic rehabilitation of the liberated territories, taking constructive measures, implementing infrastructure projects, organizing socially and industrially important enterprises - all these are, of course, issues that require considerable resources and time, and labor. But there are issues that are more important and of strategic importance for the implementation of all this. Solving the problems of economic development and settlement in any territory, primarily the implementation of road projects and the opening of communications, are essential conditions. Along with these, two new economic regions have been created in the liberated territories, namely the Karabakh and East Zangezur economic regions, and in general the number of economic regions in our country has increased from 12 to 14 [5]. The efficient use of resources of newly created economic regions, the construction of modern facilities in these areas, the construction of residential areas, the formation of recreational areas, the organization of areas containing utility services, and the formation of conditions that can generally ensure normal living require continuous work, a lot of money and labor [6]. In addition, the first noticeable large-scale projects in the liberated territories were related to transport projects, and we would like to touch on such projects in more detail.

It should be noted that currently the largest projects in Karabakh are related to transport projects. Fuzuli International Airport, one of the largest airports in this region, was built in a very short time - 8 months

and put into operation in September 2021. This can also be viewed as a global transport project implemented at a very high speed. The construction and commissioning of such an international airport in a short time shows that the Azerbaijani state is determined to intensively revive our lands liberated from occupation and to maximally accelerate the socio-economic development of the region. Later, the construction of the Zangilan International Airport and the creation of a similar transport and logistics infrastructure led to the formation of another large transport project and the commissioning of this airport in 2022. All this shows that measures to more efficiently use the resources in the region, include them in economic turnover and deploy productive forces, and ensure a high-level settlement of former internally displaced persons within the framework of the Great Return are already entering an intensive phase. It is known that another such project is being implemented in Lachin, and the commissioning of three international airports in the future will not only increase the transport and logistics capabilities of the region, but also have a positive impact on accelerating the socio-economic construction processes, and these are already actively taking place [7].

At the same time, the implementation of 17 large and small transport projects, for example, the construction of the Ahmadbeyli-Fuzuli-Shusha Victory Road - a victory road consisting of very modern engineering structures, as well as the implementation of several road projects connecting the Kalbajar and Lachin regions with other liberated territories, the construction of tunnels in areas with complex relief, the construction of new roads will ultimately create an additional incentive for the acceleration of integrative processes in the region and the creation of a network of enterprises, and the settlement of the population. In this regard, in the coming years, we will witness more bold steps being taken, more intensive measures being taken in terms of population settlement, and the acceleration of the Great Return [8].

We believe that one of the most important projects among these projects is the Zangezur transport corridor. In general, the Zangezur transport corridor is currently of great importance from the point of view of opening up transport-logistics and communications at the international level, integrating countries, regions, continents and intensifying international trade processes, accelerating purchase and sale processes and flows of goods, accelerating investment flows and raising trade and economic relations between continents to a new stage, optimizing related costs, and these factors, in turn, are arguments that increase the role of the Zangezur global transport corridor. In a situation where modern global economic and technological challenges are accelerating, these mentioned are considered important elements [9, p.361].

In fact, the opening of the Zangezur transport corridor is also in the interest of major powers, including the European Union. It is in the interest of China, one of the countries with the largest economies at the forefront of the global economy, and all this includes the relevance and strategic importance of the Zangezur transport corridor. As a result of the disruption of land

connections between the Turkic states, serious problems have arisen in the integration of these states and the preservation of their geographical connections. In view of these factors, the opening of the Zangezur corridor is of considerable strategic importance for the Turkic states for their economic integration. The total market of the Turkic states is estimated at 1.2 trillion and this includes the Turkish economy, which is among the top 15 economies in the world, the economy of Kazakhstan, which has a fairly strong economy in Central Asia, as well as the economies of Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, Kyrgyzstan and Azerbaijan. In general, there are sufficient resources, natural reserves, underground and surface wealth in the territories of the Turkic-speaking states. Nature has endowed the Turkic states with sufficient resources. There are oil and gas fields in Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Azerbaijan and Turkmenistan. It is gratifying that recently Turkey has started producing natural gas in the Black Sea. These are the national treasures that nature has bestowed upon the Turkic states, and we believe that with the opening of the Zangezur global transport corridor, the integration of the Turkic states will reach a new level and stage.

This will not only expand ordinary economic relations, but also the unification of the Turkic world, the closer convergence of Turkish culture and Turkish customs and traditions, the intensive occurrence of travel, trade and commerce processes, and as a result, the potential for creating new opportunities in the implementation of economic projects of Turkic-speaking states and increasing their economic power will be formed [10].

The multiplicative role of the Zangezur Global Transport Corridor in the context of sustainable development in a global perspective. After the Great Karabakh Victory, a new geopolitical and geostrategic situation has emerged in the region, and the processes are continuing rapidly. In particular, the opening of the Zangezur corridor, in accordance with the November 10 Statement, is in line with the strategic interests of neighboring states with strong, reliable partnership relations in political and economic activities, such as Russia and Azerbaijan. The Zangezur corridor is a very important communication hub connecting the Eurasian space with each other, the gate to the Caucasus and Central Asia. At the informal Summit of the Cooperation Council of Turkic-Speaking States held in a videoconference format on March 31 this year, Azerbaijani President Ilham Aliyev spoke about the geopolitical and geostrategic importance of the Zangezur corridor: "The Zangezur corridor is a historical achievement. The fact that this issue is especially reflected in the Trilateral Statement is also our great political victory... Zangezur, an ancient Azerbaijani land, will now play the role of unifying the Turkic world."

At the same time, this corridor will significantly expand the opportunities for the Russian Federation to expand trade and economic relations with Turkey, a very important strategic partner for it. According to preliminary estimates, the value of cargo transported through the Zangezur corridor will be measured in billions of dollars, and this will cover cargo transportation, trade and economic relations, and wider commodity

markets in the region. If we add the huge Chinese market to this, we can predict that this figure will increase. Interestingly, up to \$ 1.2 trillion of this market falls on the share of Turkic-speaking countries, led by Turkey. As we have noted, Azerbaijan and Russia will have the opportunity to benefit from these important commodity markets to the maximum. Through the Zangezur corridor, Azerbaijan and Russia will have the potential to strengthen their integrative relations with numerous world countries. By increasing the intensity of cargo transportation between West and East, North and South, expanding international trade operations, and significantly developing the transport and logistics sector, additional real potential will be formed for increasing the political and economic power of Azerbaijan and Russia. It is currently known that large-scale construction work is being carried out in the newly created Karabakh and East Zangezur economic regions after our historic victory in the Patriotic War. [11]. Measures are being taken to ensure the "Great Return", social infrastructure is being formed, in short, life is boiling and reviving in the territories liberated from occupation. The most important of these projects is the Zangezur global transport corridor. In general, the Zangezur corridor is currently of great importance from the point of view of opening up transport-logistics and communications at the international level, integrating countries, regions, continents and intensifying international trade processes, accelerating commodity and investment flows, raising trade and economic relations between continents to a new stage, and optimizing related costs. These factors, in turn, are arguments that increase the role of the Zangezur corridor. In a situation where modern global economic and technological challenges are accelerating, these are considered important elements. At the same time, the recent contradictory events in the world, wars, sanctions against Russia by the US and European Union countries, deterioration of relations with China, and unconstructive behavior of some states in the region have formed new views on global transport corridors. It is also important to note how many strong countries have an interest in opening a communication route like the Zangezur corridor [12].

In our opinion, the opening of the Zangezur transport corridor is actually in the interest of major powers, including the European Union. It is in the interest of China, one of the largest economies leading the global economy. However, I believe that the opening of the Zangezur global transport corridor is primarily of historical importance and strategic significance for the Turkic states. The Turkic states have been separated from each other for hundreds of years, and as a result of the severance of land connections between them, serious problems have arisen in the integration of these states and the preservation of their geographical connections. Russia and Iran, taking as an opportunity the collapse of the Ottoman Empire after the First World War and the need for a certain amount of time for the formation of Turkey as an independent state, treacherously managed to injure the geography of the Turkic world. It was the Russian Bolsheviks who, by giving the territory between Azerbaijan and Nakhchivan to Armenia, managed to cut the land borders between

Azerbaijan and Turkey, which created very serious obstacles to the development of Azerbaijan, and these problems still persist. [13].

As a logical consequence of the Great Karabakh Victory, historical events are taking place in the region, in Turkish geography and in our country. The processes of revitalization of the Karabakh and East Zangezur economic regions, established by the initiative of the President of the country and the Decree dated July 7, 2021, have entered an intensive phase. A large-scale infrastructure network is being created, residential areas are being built, and projects based on "smart" technologies are being implemented. The commissioning of Fuzuli International Airport is of strategic importance as the largest transport project in the region. Currently, work on various transport projects, the creation of industrial infrastructure and the organization of a free economic zone is accelerating in many directions. However, along with all this, the world's attention is focused on the Zangezur corridor, and there are serious grounds for this. The opening of the Zangezur corridor is of great importance not only for the strategic interests of Russia and Azerbaijan, but also for other regional countries and Turkic-speaking states within the Turkish geography. The total value of cargo that will circulate through the Zangezur corridor is expected to be significantly higher, and the volume of cargo transportation and import-export operations in the region will increase many times. Taking into account the large-scale Chinese market factor, which has shown serious interest in the productive use of the Zangezur corridor, the geo-economic importance of this corridor has increased considerably [14].

Considering that today the annual volume of trade turnover between the European Union and China is approximately \$560 billion and the Zangezur corridor is an optimal route for both of these poles, the importance of the corridor becomes somewhat clearer. At the same time, by benefiting from the Zangezur corridor, it is possible to predict that integration between the Turkic-speaking states - Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan and Turkmenistan, led by Turkey, which has a common market of \$1.2 trillion, will expand in a short time and foreign trade turnover will increase significantly [15]. At the VIII Summit of the Cooperation Council of Turkic-speaking States, Azerbaijani President Ilham Aliyev said: "...in 1920, the Soviet authorities, by tearing Zangezur from Azerbaijan and giving it to Armenia, disrupted the geographical connection of the Turkic world, and anyone can see this by looking at the map. Today, we are restoring this geography. "With the implementation of transport and communication projects, we are reconnecting and uniting this geography, and I hope that we will succeed in this until the end" [16; 17; 18]. Yes, historical justice is being restored, and Turkic-speaking states are gaining unprecedented opportunities to integrate more closely, increase their economic potential, and strengthen their geographical position.

Result. Thus, the creation of the Zangezur global transport corridor will strengthen the Turkic world and allow the Turkic-speaking states to play a more important role in the world economy and world politics in

the new conditions arising in the organization of the Turkic-speaking states.

- The commissioning of the Zangezur corridor will not only expand ordinary economic relations, but also unite the Turkic world, bring its culture and traditions closer together, intensify travel and trade processes, and as a result, create new opportunities for the implementation of economic projects of Turkic-speaking states and increase their economic power;

- The opening of the Zangezur corridor will also strengthen the Turkic world, allow them to play a more important role in the world economy and world politics in the new conditions arising in the organization of Turkic-speaking states;

- As a result of the realization of this historical opportunity, the Zangezur corridor will bring the countries of the region closer together, and by uniting the Turkic geography, it will significantly increase the economic power, competitiveness and international image of our country in the region and the world;

- Most importantly, it will enable the economic progress of Turkic-speaking states, increase the standard of living of the population, strengthen economic and national security and defense, intensify transfer exchanges for the development of high technologies, and attract new resources for the preservation and development of the values of the Turkic world, etc.

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